

Colour of Complex Diazoles. Part IV. Constitution of Thiele's Supposed *o*-Benzylene-1:3-benziminazole.

By MANGESH V. BETRABET AND GOPÁL CHANDRA CHAKRAVARTI.

In connection with our investigation upon the absorption spectra of various condensed iminazoles, it became necessary to prepare a quantity of *o*-benzylene-1:3-benziminazole. This compound has been synthesised by Thiele and Falk (*Annalen*, 1906, 347, 112) by condensing phthalaldehyde with *o*-phenylene diamine. They described it as a colourless crystalline compound, m. p. 210°. Normally the reaction mentioned above would lead to the formation of a condensed eight-membered ring system (I).

But Thiele and Falk assigned the formula (II) to the product of this reaction, because, on oxidation with permanganate it easily changed into *o*-benzoylenebenziminazole (III), a compound of definite constitution. But in spite of this strong evidence in support of formula (II) it is difficult to comprehend how an atom of hydrogen from one methine group in the compound (I) travels over to the other methine group, converting the latter into a methylene group as in the compound (II). There is no reason why such a hydrogen atom should be labile. These facts led us to synthesise *o*-benzoylenebenzi-

minazole by a method which would leave no doubt as regards its constitution.

It is now well known that ketonic condensed iminazoles like (III) can be very easily prepared by fusing the anhydrides of dibasic acids with diamines or by boiling them in absolute alcoholic solutions (Bistrzycki and Lecco, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 425; Bistrzycki and Fässler, *ibid.*, 1923, 6, 521; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 18; Chakravarti and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1925, 1, 330). In a similar manner we supposed that the condensation between phthalide and *o*-phenylene diamine would lead to the formation of the compound (II) according to the following general scheme:—

But when phthalide was fused with *o*-phenylene diamine a compound, m.p. above 300°, which is proved to be benzimidazole-2-benzyl-*o*-phenylene diamine (V) containing four nitrogen atoms was obtained. Evidently two molecules of the diamine had condensed with one of the phthalide. On boiling together the phthalide and the diamine another product, m.p. 162° (VI), also containing four nitrogen atoms resulted. This, on fusion, lost a molecule of water and was converted into (V). Hence the reactions take the following course:

On treating *o*-oxymethylbenzoic acid with *o*-phenylene diamine in the presence of 4*N*-hydrochloric acid, following a method similar to that of Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 2398), benzimidazole-2-*o*-oxymethylbenzene (IV) and benzimidazole-2-benzyl-*o*-phenylene diamine (V) were obtained. But the yield of the desired compound (IV) was extremely poor. Next, when we treated *o*-oxymethylbenzoic acid with the diamine in cold absolute alcohol, we obtained an addition compound *o*'-aminophenylammonium-*o*-oxymethylbenzoate (VII) which contained two atoms of nitrogen. On boiling this compound with absolute alcohol it lost a molecule of water and was converted into *o*-oxymethyl-*o*'-aminobenzanilide (VIII) as follows:—

The condensation of phthalide and the diamine in cold absolute alcohol also gave the compound (VIII) in good yield.

The dehydration of *o*-oxymethyl-*o*'-aminobenzanilide with acetic anhydride or by fusion, yielded *o*-benzylene-1:3-benzimidazole (II)

with hot dilute alkaline solution and water and finally extracted with alcohol to remove soluble impurities. The residue crystallised from excess of boiling xylene in colourless crystalline aggregates. *Benzimidazole-2-benzyl-o-phenylene diamine* (V) melts above 300°. It dissolves in acids yielding a blue solution, from which by neutralisation the original compound can be obtained. It is not hydrolysed by acids. (Found: C, 76.28; H, 6.35; N, 17.45. $C_{20}H_{18}N_4$ requires C, 76.43; H, 6.29; N, 17.87 per cent.).

Condensation of Phthalide with o-Phenylene diamine in absolute Alcohol by Boiling.—Phthalide (2.7 g.) and *o*-phenylene diamine (4.3 g.) were dissolved in 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol and refluxed for three hours on a water-bath. On cooling very fine colourless crystalline plates were deposited. These were recrystallised from the same solvent; *o*-aminophenylaminomethyl-*o*-aminobenzanilide (VI) gave a m.p. 162°. This compound responded to the tests for primary amines. (Found: C, 72.09; H, 6.13; N, 16.62. $C_{20}H_{20}ON_4$ requires C, 72.29; H, 6.02; N, 16.87 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative was prepared by dissolving the compound in glacial acetic acid, adding acetyl chloride drop by drop to the mixture, and finally refluxing it for an hour. The precipitate that came down was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 135-136°. (Found: N, 13.21. $C_{24}H_{24}O_3N_4$ requires N, 13.46 per cent.).

Fusion of the Compound (VI).—This compound (1 g.) was heated in a test tube at 180-185° for two hours. On cooling it was extracted with alcohol and the residue crystallised from excess of xylene in colourless crystalline aggregates. This compound had the same properties as those possessed by *benzimidazole-2-benzyl-o-phenylene diamine* (V), m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 17.47. $C_{20}H_{18}N_4$ requires N, 17.87 per cent.).

Condensation of o-Phenylene diamine with o-Oxymethylbenzoic Acid in the Presence of 4N-HCl.—*o*-Oxymethylbenzoic acid (9 g.), *o*-phenylene diamine (6 g.) and 100 c.c. of 4N-HCl solution were mixed and shaken well for half an hour and finally boiled under reflux for an hour. On cooling a crystalline mass deposited which was filtered and crystallised from hot water. This compound was identified to be phthalide, m. p. 73° (yield, 6 g.). The filtrate was treated with 50 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution till it was alkaline. The precipitate which came down was a mixture of *o*-phenylene diamine and *benzimidazole-2-benzyl-o-phenylene diamine* (V).

The latter compound m.p. above 300° was isolated, crystallised and analysed. (Found: N, 17·46. $C_{20}H_{16}N_4$ requires N, 17·87 per cent.). The filtrate was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid till it was acid to congo-red. The precipitate was a mixture of phthalide and *bensiminasole-2-oxymethylbenzene* (IV). This crude product was extracted with benzene and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 287-289°. The yield was very poor. (Found: N, 12·7. $C_{12}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12·5 per cent.).

Condensation of o-Phenylene diamine with o-Oxymethylbenzoic Acid in cold absolute Alcohol.—*o*-Oxymethylbenzoic acid (7·6 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and mixed with a solution of *o*-phenylene diamine (5·4 g.). This mixture was kept overnight in a stoppered bottle upon a shaking machine at the room temperature. The next day the whole of it had precipitated as a flocculent mass. It was filtered and crystallised from a small quantity of absolute alcohol in colourless aggregates. On analysis they were found to be an *additive product* (VII) of the acid and the amine, m.p. 103-104°. They were very soluble in water and alcohol but insoluble in inert solvents. (Found: N, 10·90. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10·76 per cent.).

This compound on boiling with absolute alcohol for three hours was converted into a compound, m.p. 150-152° of colourless crystalline nature. This was proved to be *o-oxymethyl-o'-aminobenzanilide* (VIII). (Found: N, 11·82. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11·61 per cent.).

Condensation of o-Phenylene diamine with Phthalide in cold Absolute Alcohol.—Phthalide (6·7 g.) was dissolved in a small quantity of absolute alcohol. The mixture was kept in a stoppered bottle, overnight, with good shaking and filtered. The precipitate was crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms. The *o-oxymethyl-o'-aminobenzanilide* (VIII) melted at 152°. (Found: N, 11·51. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11·61 per cent.).

o-Benzylene-1:3-bensiminasole (II).—*o*-Oxymethyl-*o'*-aminobenzanilide (5 g.) was heated in a hard glass test tube at 180-190° for a few minutes till there was no more frothing. On cooling it was extracted with absolute alcohol when a portion did not dissolve. This was filtered and crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless crystals and identified to be *bensiminasole-2-benzyl-o-phenylene diamine* (V), m.p. above 330°. From the alcoholic extract was obtained after crystallisation from xylene, colourless prismatic rosettes of *o-benzylene-1:3-bensiminasole*, m.p. 185°. Repeated crystallisations from other

solvents did not raise the m.p. higher. This compound was also prepared by heating *o*-oxymethyl-*o'*-aminobenzamide with acetic anhydride for half an hour. The crude product was decolourised with animal charcoal and then crystallised from xylene. It does not form a picrate or a chloroplatinate. (Found: C, 81.87; H, 5.82; N, 18.91. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 81.55; H, 4.86; N, 13.78 per cent.).

Condensation of Phthalide with Ethylene Diamine.—Ethylene diamine (25 g.) and phthalide (6.7 g.) each dissolved in a small quantity of absolute alcohol, were mixed together and shaken well for some time. The reaction was completed in a little time and granular colourless crystals deposited. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless crystalline aggregates. The *o*-oxymethyl-aminoethylbenzamide melted at 179-180°. (Found: N, 14.54. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.7 per cent.).

Dihydroiminazole-2-oxymethylbenzene.—*o*-Oxymethylaminoethyl benzamide (5 g.) was boiled with 40 c.c. of absolute alcohol for three hours, when on cooling a colourless crystalline compound was obtained, m.p. 210-211°. (Found: N, 15.72. $C_{10}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 15.9 per cent.).

Phenylenedihydroiminazole (X).—Dihydroiminazole-2-oxymethyl (5 g.) was heated with a slight excess of acetic anhydride for an hour. The excess of anhydride was evaporated on a water-bath and the residue was extracted several times with ether and crystallised from alcohol in beautiful colourless short prisms, m.p. 152-153°. (Found: C, 75.88; H, 6.40; N, 17.51. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 75.95; H, 6.35; N, 17.7 per cent.).

*Condensation of Phthalaldehyde with *o*-Phenylene Diamine and the Formation of *o*-Benzylphenylene Diamine.*—Phthalaldehyde was prepared according to the method of Thiele and Guntner (*Annalen*, 1906, 347, 102) with slight alterations in minor details, which gave long colourless needles on repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether, m.p. 58° (sharp). Thiele describes it as a yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 56°.

It was condensed with *o*-phenylene diamine according to the method of Thiele and Falk (*loc. cit.*). The product on repeated crystallisation from alcohol gave beautiful colourless rosettes, m.p. 213.5°. Thiele gives the m.p. as 210°. This compound does not give any tests for free aldehyde group. It easily forms a picrate and a platinum salt.

Oxidation of Benzyl-o-phenylene Diamine(I).—The oxidation was carried out according to the method of Thiele and Falk (*loc. cit.*) and gave *o*-benzoylene-1:3-benziminazole (III) yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 211°. It was identified by a mixed melting point with the compound prepared according to the method of Bistrzycki (*loc. cit.*).

Oxidation of o-Benzylenebenziminazole (II).—*o*-Benzylenebenziminazole (10 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of benzene and to this was added drop by drop a solution of 5 per cent. potassium permanganate with 2 per cent. sulphuric acid, until it was no longer decolourised when the oxidation was complete, the manganese dioxide was dissolved by means sulphur dioxide. The benzene solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue treated with hot water. The insoluble yellow residue was filtered and crystallised from alcohol. Yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 211°. This was identified with *o*-benzoylene benziminazole (III) obtained in the previous experiment by a mixed melting point.

Oxidation of o-Benzylenedihydroiminazole.—The method of oxidation described in the previous experiment was followed; but the percentages of KMnO_4 and H_2SO_4 were 3 and 1 respectively, because, otherwise total decomposition took place. The crude oxidation product melted indefinitely at 170-180°. The residue was extracted with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate, residue extracted with hot benzene, and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Colourless prisms, m.p. 229-230°. The yield of *o*-benzoylene dihydroiminazole (XI) was very low. (Found: C, 69.54; H, 4.8; N, 16.51. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{ON}_2$ requires C, 69.76; H, 4.65; N, 16.2 per cent.). The other products of oxidation were too small for further examination. *o*-Benzoylenedihydroiminazole has also been obtained by condensing phthalic anhydride with ethylene diamine and the mixed melting point corresponds to 229°. The preparation of this compound among others will form the subject of a separate communication.